

IC Modelling and Analysis in Geotechnical Engineering

Model 35

Contents:

IC MAGE M35 is a user-defined model for PLAXIS built using the IC MAGE UMIP framework which uses a hypoelastic formulation to simulate the non-linear stiffness of struts, which can be affected by slack in various components of the system. The envisaged modelling approach requires the explicit modelling of the prop using solid elements to which this material model must be assigned. Starting with no stiffness, the model uses an hyperbolic law, with the stiffness value increasing asymptotically to its theoretical value.

Disclaimer:

IC MAGE soil models undergo extensive testing and validation but can never be guaranteed to be free of errors. IC MAGE soil models are employed at the users' own risk and the authors of these models cannot be held responsible or liable for any errors arising from their application.

Document history:

Date	Revision	
2026-01-20	1.0	Initial publication
2026-02-20	1.1	Additional hardening parameters
2026-03-21	1.2	Irreversible unloading/reloading behaviour introduced

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IC MAGE M35

Non-linear stiffness model for struts

PARAMETERS

P01	$k_t (FL^{-1}L^{-1})$	> 0	Theoretical stiffness per meter of the propping system
P02	$A_{model} (L^2L^{-1})$	> 0	Modelled cross-sectional area of the prop per meter (modelled thickness)
P03	$L_p (L)$	> 0	Length of the prop (see notes)
P04	δ_a or $\varepsilon_{ax,a}$		Prop shortening (> 0) or prop strain (< 0) controlling the rate of activation
P05	$E_{min} (FL^{-2})$	≥ 0	Minimum elastic stiffness
P06	<i>PropAxis</i>	1, 2, 3	Axis defining axial direction (1 – x, 2 – y, 3 – z)
P07	F_{pre}	≥ 0	Parameter defining any pre-loading applied to the strut (needs to be used in conjunction with actual forces applied to the wall)
P08	<i>Unload</i>	0,1	Switch defining unloading/reloading behaviour (0 – nonlinear behaviour, 1 – irreversible behaviour)
P09	<i>SettingsFile</i>	0,1	Switch for using a settings file (see notes)
P10	<i>OutputControl</i>	0,1,2,3,4	Controls the desired output by the model
P11	<i>EnergyCalc</i>	0,1 → 9, 11 → 19	No energy calculated if 0, see UMIP for other options

DEFAULT VALUES

Not applicable for this model.

HARDENING PARAMETERS

HP01	<i>InitVar</i>	Initialisation variable (required by UMIP)
HP02	$\varepsilon_{ax,0}$	Axial strain when the material is activated
HP03	ε_{ax}	Current axial strain
HP04	δ	Current shortening
HP05	$E_{current}$	Current stiffness
HP06	k_{eff}	Current effective stiffness of the strut
HP07	k_{ave}	Current average stiffness of the strut (i.e. from loading)
HP08	F_{strut}	Current expected force (obtained from hardening parameters)
HP09	$\varepsilon_{ax,max}$	Maximum compressive axial strain
HP10	δ_{max}	Maximum compression reached by the strut

HP11	$\varepsilon_{ax,lim}$	Limit compressive axial strain linked to the use of E_{min}
HP12	δ_{lim}	Limit compression linked to the use of E_{min} for irreversible behaviour
HP13 – HP45		Energy calculation (only if P10 <i>EnergyCalc</i> is set to ≥ 1.0)

MODEL FORMULATION

This model is formulated based on a strain-dependent stiffness measured in the axial direction, defined by *P07 PropAxis*, of the prop. This assumes that all the slacks and imperfections in the propping system, including but not limited to the connections between the props and the walls, can be simulated as being distributed throughout the prop simulated using this material model.

The behaviour of the prop, when modelled with this material model, is expected to follow a hyperbolic function with a zero effective stiffness at the start of loading, increasing asymptotically towards a theoretical value k_t , defined as a uniformly distributed stiffness along the out-of-plane direction, i.e. in $kN/m/m$. The adopted function is defined analytically as:

$$F_{strut} = k_t \cdot \left[\frac{\delta^2}{\delta + \delta_a} \right] \quad (1)$$

where F is the prop load, δ is its shortening, and δ_a is a model parameter.

The average (or secant) stiffness since the start of loading can be directly obtained from this expression by dividing by the current shortening:

$$k_{ave} = \frac{F_{strut}}{\delta} = k_t \cdot \left[\frac{\delta}{\delta + \delta_a} \right] \quad (2)$$

To obtain the effective prop stiffness function, k_{eff} , the derivative of the expression for the force is required:

$$k_{eff} = \frac{dF_{strut}}{d\delta} = k_t \cdot \delta \cdot \left[\frac{\delta + 2 \cdot \delta_a}{(\delta + \delta_a)^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

This behaviour will be modelled using solid elements. Therefore, this model needs to be formulated in terms of Young's modulus, with the corresponding stiffness being given by:

$$k_{eff} = \frac{E_{eff} \cdot A_{model}}{L_p} \quad (4)$$

where A_{model} is the cross-sectional area of the prop in the numerical model. For example, in 2D analyses, this will be the thickness of the geometric polygon defining the prop, i.e. the dimension of the prop measured in the direction perpendicular to that defined by *P07 PropAxis*. In the equation above, L_p is the prop length, which is assumed to be the same in the model as in the engineering problem.

Equating the two previous equations to each other, yields:

$$k_t \cdot \delta \cdot \left[\frac{\delta + 2 \cdot \delta_a}{(\delta + \delta_a)^2} \right] = \frac{E_{eff} \cdot A_{model}}{L_p} \quad (5)$$

which, rearranged, leads to:

$$E_{eff} = k_t \cdot \delta \cdot \frac{L_p}{A_{model}} \cdot \left[\frac{\delta + 2 \cdot \delta_a}{(\delta + \delta_a)^2} \right] \quad (6)$$

The prop response has to be defined in terms of axial strain, rather than prop shortening, which can be achieved by substituting $\delta = \varepsilon_{ax} \cdot L_p$. Equally, $\delta_a = \varepsilon_{ax,a} \cdot L_p$. Substituting and simplifying, leads to:

$$E_{eff} = k_t \cdot \varepsilon_{ax} \cdot \frac{L_p}{A_{model}} \cdot \left[\frac{\varepsilon_{ax} + 2 \cdot \varepsilon_{ax,a}}{(\varepsilon_{ax} + \varepsilon_{ax,a})^2} \right] \quad (7)$$

where $\varepsilon_{ax,a}$ is either specified directly in *P04* (if a negative value is used) or obtained by converting the value of δ_a in *P04* (if a positive value is used) to an extension using $\varepsilon_{ax,a} = \delta_a / L_p$.

The stiffness value given in Equation (7) is subjected to a minimum value given in *P05*:

$$E_{eff} \geq E_{min} \quad (8)$$

Lastly, note that, to avoid effects arising from plane strain assumptions, the Poisson's ratio of this material is assumed to be always 0.0.

If there is a need to apply pre-loading, then a force should be introduced in the numerical analysis in the phase before the activation of the strut **and should remain in place**. The value of the force applied should be introduced in *P07* and based on that value, the compression is initialised by inverting Equation 1, i.e. placing the current stress point in the compression-force curve at the pre-load level:

$$\delta_{initial} = \frac{F_{pre} + \sqrt{F_{pre}^2 + 4 \cdot k_t \cdot \delta_a}}{2 \cdot k_t} \quad (9)$$

which is then converted to an initial value of the *HP03* using:

$$\varepsilon_{ax} = \varepsilon_{ax} + \frac{\delta_{initial}}{L_p} \quad (10)$$

There is a switch in *P08* defining the unloading/reloading behaviour. If *P08* = 0, then a non-linear elastic formulation is used, and all deformations are recoverable (i.e. the compression-force curve is unique and is followed independently of whether the compression of the strut is increasing or decreasing).

If, however, *P08* = 1, then the model keeps track of the maximum compression ever to be applied to the strut in *HP09* = δ_{max} and, should unloading take place, the stiffness, rather than being determined by the current compression, it is determined by that corresponding to δ_{max} .

There is a lower limit to the stiffness that can be reached controlled by E_{min} . This is activated once the compression of the strut drops below a given value, calculated by:

$$\varepsilon_{ax,lim} = \frac{E_{max} \varepsilon_{max} - \frac{F_{max}}{A_{model}}}{E_{max} - E_{lim}} \quad (11)$$

If $\varepsilon_{ax} < \varepsilon_{ax,lim}$ then $E_{eff} = E_{lim} = 99\% E_{max}$ until such stage where $\varepsilon_{ax} > \varepsilon_{ax,lim}$. In the equation above, E_{max} and F_{max} are the stiffness and force corresponding to ε_{max} , respectively.

MODEL USAGE

1. *P09 OutputControl* determines the level of output desired from the model integration:

$P09 = 0$	Full output with details on the integration of the model and warnings (default).
$P09 = 1$	Full output with details on the integration of the model but without warnings.
$P09 = 2$	Brief output consisting only of the progress of the calculation (step and iteration) and warnings.
$P09 = 3$	Brief output consisting only of the progress of the calculation (step and iteration) but without warnings.
$P09 = 4$	No output will be produced

2. If $P10$ *EnergyCalc* is set to ≥ 1.0 , the *UMIP* will add 33 new hardening parameters to the constitutive model to calculate and store energy-related quantities. More information can be found in the documentation of the *UMIP* but of greatest interest are the current damping ratio, the secant shear stiffness and the secant bulk stiffness. This module is particularly useful if the model is being used for pseudo-static or dynamic analyses. Note that the use of this option increases slightly memory and processing requirements.

3. Note that this model simulates a very large change in stiffness due to the rapid activation of the stiffness (this is particularly the case for small positive values of parameter $P04$ δ_a or $\varepsilon_{ax,a}$). Because of this, the internal control for its integration is set to **always** use the maximum stiffness to generate the stiffness matrix. Therefore, the running times due to slow convergence may be large for the phases where the strut is being constructed/activated and a large number of iterations **and** steps may be required. This can be deactivated via a settings file, by setting $F06 = 0$, though this may lead to divergence if the strut system increases rapidly (e.g. large steps). This can be mitigated by setting a large number in $F07$ (e.g. 5000) or by setting special option to a relatively large integer (e.g. between 5 and 9).

4. The use of the special option follows the general philosophy set out in the *UMIP* manual, adapted to this model according to the following rules:

The general format of the special option is a 9-digit integer:

$$I_9 I_8 I_7 I_6 I_5 I_4 I_3 I_2 I_1$$

Value	Description
I_1	Elastic stiffness matrix control
1 to 9	Elastic stiffness matrix is scaled up by a factor given by $100 \cdot I_1\%$
I_2	Energy quantities control
1	Resets all energy-related quantities ($HP06 - HP38$) if $P10 \geq 1$
I_3	High Cycle Accumulation control
–	Not implemented
I_4	Plastic strain tensor
–	Not implemented

Value	Description
<i>I</i> ₅ – Void ratio	
–	Not implemented
<i>I</i> ₆ – Elastic stiffness of the material	
1	Removes the strain history (<i>HP02</i> to <i>HP04</i>), simulating a reinstallation of the prop.
<i>I</i> ₇ – Elastic hardening parameters	
–	Not implemented
<i>I</i> ₈ – Yield surface	
–	Not implemented
<i>I</i> ₉ – Plastic hardening parameters	
–	Not implemented

Note that if a negative value is given to the special option, then the UMIP will interpret this as a request to use the maximum stiffness matrix, independently of the value of *I*₁, provided *I*₁ > 0. The use of the maximum possible stiffness results in the most stable calculation, though a large number of iterations is likely to be required as convergence will be slower. This also applies to values of *I*₁ > 5, though there is no general rule to this.

5. A text file input approach is available to define values of parameters which could not be included in the list of parameters due to PLAXIS' limit of 50 model parameters. To use this feature, *P08 SettingsFile* should be set to 1.0 and a file called *M35.settings.txt* should be placed within the folder *C:\icmage* with the following contents:

Control parameter			Default value	Description
<i>F01</i>	<i>MinElasticSteps</i>	≥ 0	2	Minimum no of elastic integration steps
<i>F02</i>	<i>MaxElasticSteps</i>	≥ 0	1000	Maximum no of elastic integration steps
<i>F03</i>	<i>NLElasticTol</i>	≥ 0	1 × 10 ⁻⁶	Elastic integration tolerance
<i>F04</i>	<i>ElasticHPControl</i>	0, 1	0	0 – changes in elastic hardening parameters do not affect elastic integration 1 – changes in elastic hardening parameters affect elastic integration
<i>F05</i>	<i>Solution control</i>	0, 1	1	0 – the stiffness matrix is generated only at the start of the phase 1 – the stiffness matrix is generated at the start of every step
<i>F06</i>	<i>Unloading control</i>	0, 1	1	0 – the stiffness matrix is generated based on current elastic stiffness 1 – the stiffness matrix is generated based on maximum elastic stiffness
<i>F07</i>	<i>Stiffness scalar</i>	≥ 10	120	Scalar used to increase the elastic matrix in percentage. Larger values improve the

Control parameter			Default value	Description
				stability of the solution but slows down convergence.
<i>F08</i>	<i>Debug switch</i>	0, 1	0	0 – no additional debug information 1 – full debug information (note that this will generate very large output files)

Note that, with the exception of F04, F05, F06 and F08, if a value of zero is used, then the default value (or the one in the graphical input if it has been specified) will be used. Since a value of 0 is a possible value for F04, F05, F06 and F08, the desired value must always be specified. Moreover, the file must always have the full list of parameters being given as the code expects to find a column with 8 values, returning an error if a smaller number of parameters is found. Lastly, **note that parameters specified via the GUI will always take precedence.**